

PSDI

PHYSICAL SCIENCES
DATA INFRASTRUCTURE

Enabling Best Practices in Research Data Curation in Physical Sciences: Recommendations on the Role for PSDI

Agnes Jasinska, Digital Curation Centre, UK

Ian Bruno and Cian Dingle, Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, UK

2 March 2026

1	Introduction	4
1.1	About the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)	4
1.2	Purpose and Scope of the Report	4
1.3	Authors	4
1.3.1	About the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC)	4
1.3.2	About the Digital Curation Centre (DCC)	5
2	Background and Context	5
2.1	Definitions	5
2.2	Curation Guidelines vs. Implementation of Such Guidelines	6
3	Roles, Responsibilities, and Skills	7
3.1	Key Roles	8
3.1.1	Data Curators and Repository Managers	8
3.1.2	Researchers	8
3.1.3	Data Stewards and Other Research Support Staff	9
3.1.4	Technicians and Facilities	10
3.1.5	Research Software Developers	10
3.1.6	Publishers	11
3.1.7	Funders	11
3.1.8	National and International Infrastructure Initiatives	12
3.1.9	Instrument and Tool Providers	12
3.1.10	Professional Organizations and Scholarly Societies	13
3.2	How PSDI Can Support and Collaborate with Practitioners	13
4	Reference Frameworks	14
4.1	FAIR Data Principles	14
4.1.1	FAIR for AI and AI for FAIR	15
4.1.2	Recommendations for PSDI	16
4.2	The TRUST Principles and Related Frameworks	17
4.2.1	CoreTrustSeal Criteria	17
4.2.2	Current European Project Landscape	19
4.2.3	Recommendations for PSDI	19
5	Data Curation Case Studies from across Domains	20
5.1	Lessons from Crystallography	20
5.1.1	Automated Curation Workflows	21
5.1.2	Raw Data	22
5.1.3	Validation	22
5.2	Data Curation at Dryad	23
5.3	The Data Curation Network	24
5.4	NFDI4Chem	25
5.5	Biodata Resources – Addressing Continuity Challenges	26
5.6	Discipline-specific Data Management Plans	27

5.7	Data Curation and the Long Tail of Physical Sciences.....	28
5.8	Machine-Actionable Data Interoperability in Chemical Sciences.....	29
5.9	Cross-domain Interoperability	29
6	Recommendations and Next Steps.....	30
6.1	Summary of Recommendations.....	30
6.2	Specific Recommendations.....	31
6.2.1	Community Building and Skills Development.....	31
6.2.2	Infrastructure, Tools, Standards and Services.....	31
6.2.3	Promoting and Supporting Standards.....	32
6.2.4	Bridging Industry and Academia.....	33
6.2.5	Policy, Advocacy and Strategic Engagement	33
6.2.6	Continuity and Sustainability of Activities.....	34
6.3	Skills and Expertise Required	34
6.4	Next Steps	34
7	Acknowledgements.....	35

1 Introduction

The current report is the collaborative work of the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC), the Digital Curation Centre (DCC), and the Physical Science Data Infrastructure (PSDI).

1.1 About the Physical Sciences Data Infrastructure (PSDI)

The [Physical Science Data Infrastructure \(PSDI\)](#) is a research data infrastructure and a community of researchers and other stakeholders in Physical Sciences in the United Kingdom. In addition to providing an integrated data infrastructure that directly supports researchers in the Physical Sciences in the UK to manage, transform, and share their data, PSDI also serves as a community hub and a source of expert knowledge and guidance, thus fostering knowledge exchange and collaboration and accelerating research discovery. Supporting the development of standards and best practices in domain-specific data curation, as well as relevant technical innovations, is a crucial aspect of PSDI work.

1.2 Purpose and Scope of the Report

The purpose of this report is to provide recommendations to PSDI about how it can best support the data curation needs of the UK Physical Sciences research community. It will aim to identify the role PSDI should play and the services it could provide to ensure that data outputs generated by this community are readily accessible and reusable by future generations. Whilst the report does not set out to provide a catalogue of what constitutes best practice, it may point to examples of this that could guide activities or be adopted to avoid duplication of effort.

The report is rooted in the experiences of two organisations with a long track record of engagement in research data curation: The Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC), which has deep domain experience within the Physical Sciences, and the Digital Curation Centre (DCC), which has a broad perspective across many disciplines. Building on this complementary expertise, the two organizations recently organized events under the umbrella of PSDI to bring together data curation practitioners and stakeholders, identify challenges and opportunities, exchange knowledge, and build community, notably the [PSDI Roadshow on Data Curation and Management in Physical Sciences](#) and the [RDA session on data curation at the International Data Week](#). In addition, the team members actively participated in other relevant events, such as the EOSC EDEN Data Curation Workshop and MADICES Workshop. The insights from these expert gatherings are included in this report.

1.3 Authors

1.3.1 About the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre (CCDC)

The [Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre \(CCDC\)](#) is a global leader in structural chemistry data, software, and knowledge for materials and life sciences research and development. Specializing in the collation, preservation, and application of scientific structural data, CCDC offers the renowned [Cambridge Structural Database \(CSD\)](#), a trusted resource containing fully curated organic and metal-organic structures utilized by researchers worldwide.

Enabling discovery and reuse of scientific knowledge through expert curation of data has been at the core of CCDC's activities since the inception of the CSD in 1965. Changes in the technological and societal environment have required the CCDC to adapt and evolve its curation activities to keep up with increasing throughput whilst ensuring that data remains fit for reuse by an ever-widening community of researchers. As such CCDC has an acute awareness of the challenges and practices adopted by the crystallographic community that help address these.

The CCDC is active in global research data initiatives that are aiming to establish the guidelines, standards and infrastructure needed to support data curation within and across domains including [International Union of Crystallography \(IUCr\)](#), [International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry \(IUPAC\)](#), [InChI Trust](#), [Research Data Alliance \(RDA\)](#), [CoreTrustSeal](#), and [DataCite](#). The CCDC contributed to the PSDI Pilot Study and is currently an active PSDI Partner.

1.3.2 About the Digital Curation Centre (DCC)

The [Digital Curation Centre \(DCC\)](#), based at The University of Edinburgh and University of Glasgow, is a world-leading centre of expertise in digital information curation, research data management, and open science. DCC delivers a broad range of training, resources, and tools, offers consultancy services on issues such as policy development and licensing, and provides expert advice and practical help on how to store, manage, protect and share digital research. The DCC staff are active contributors to a number of expert groups, national projects, and international consortia aimed at fostering and advancing research reproducibility and open science, including the recently completed FAIR-IMPACT and Skills4EOSC projects, and the currently active FIDELIS project, paving the ground for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

DCC is also the home of DMPonline, an open-source online tool to develop, review, and share data management plans and software management plans, as well as a community hub. And DCC organizes the annual International Digital Curation Conference (IDCC), which brings together a diverse community of researchers, data stewards, data curators, research software developers, funders, publishers, and other research professionals to exchange knowledge, discuss current trends and future directions, and establish collaborations. Overall, the development, monitoring, and dissemination of community standards and best practices for data management and data curation are at the heart of DCC's work. Like CCDC, DCC is also an active PSDI Partner.

2 Background and Context

2.1 Definitions

Before we begin our discussion of data curation in Physical Sciences, it is important to define what we mean by data curation and to distinguish it from data management and data preservation. While we acknowledge that all three terms are complex and may vary across disciplines, in this report we adopt the following working definitions based on the authorship, timing, and purpose of the relevant tasks:

- *Data management* (or research data management, RDM) refers to the organizing, storing, preserving, and sharing of research data, as well as other data-related tasks

carried out by the research team (including data stewards and/or data managers) during the research project. These activities are aimed at successful achievement of project goals as well as at making research reproducible.

- *Data curation* refers to data-related tasks carried out near or after the project completion, often by someone other than the research team (for instance, data curators at a data repository), and aimed at sharing the data with the wider scientific community and enabling data reuse, in order to maximize the new scientific knowledge and other societal benefits gained from the initial research project.
- *Data preservation* refers to those data-curation tasks that focus on ensuring the integrity of the data over the long term.
- Importantly, ***effective data management is necessary for effective data curation and preservation***. Without good data management practices during the initial research project, there may be nothing of value to curate or preserve after the project is done. In that sense, effective data curation and preservation that will eventually benefit the wider scientific community and society at large starts with and includes effective data management from the start of the research project.

Data curation also involves a number of specialized tasks that require both digital-curation expertise and domain-specific knowledge. Importantly, these curation tasks include an initial appraisal and a regular re-appraisal of the data in terms of file integrity and accessibility, completeness of the documentation and metadata, compliance with relevant laws and policies, redundancy, and potential for reuse in the context of current research activities.

Data curators can also increase the value and reuse potential of the data by curating data collections, enriching datasets with additional information from literature reviews and other sources or integrating multiple datasets to enable discipline-specific and cross-disciplinary research—sometimes referred to as *value-added curation*.

2.2 Curation Guidelines vs. Implementation of Such Guidelines

Of note, we also recognize that data curation guidelines differ from the implementation of these guidelines (including specific technical solutions). This is true in Physical Sciences as well as in any other research discipline. Thus, in the context of this report, we want to examine the need for, and benefits of, *discipline-specific guidelines vs. discipline-agnostic guidelines paired with discipline-specific implementation* for Physical Sciences in the UK.

Several related questions emerge. How much can we realistically expect researchers to learn and do with respect to data curation (as well as data management and data preservation)? Is it feasible to ask them to become experts in data curation, data management, and data preservation? Or is it sufficient for researchers to have a high level understanding of what is necessary to enable effective data management, curation, and preservation so they can adapt their practices to best support this? And finally, what is the role of automation and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in enabling and advancing best practices across the research data lifecycle, including the tasks that fall primarily under data management, data curation, and data preservation?

Guidelines are often general and abstract, and that can be both their strength and their limitation. On the one hand, general guidelines may be more flexible and lend themselves to a broader sphere of research, including cross-disciplinary research that necessarily combines the methodologies, data types, and metadata from different fields. On the other hand, guidelines that are general rather than specific and concrete may be challenging to

implement. For instance, the guideline to “Use rich metadata” may not be helpful if the person trying to implement that guideline lacks sufficient knowledge of metadata, including what metadata is and the purposes it serves, where to search for appropriate metadata schema, which tools to use to implement them, and what constitutes rich metadata in the context of specific research project or discipline.

3 Roles, Responsibilities, and Skills

As stated in the previous section on definitions, our central premise is that *effective data management (during the research project) is necessary for effective data curation and preservation (after the project is completed and the research data is shared with the wider research community).*

If this premise is true, then it follows that **multiple different roles need to contribute toward—and share the responsibility for—effective curation of research data at different points in the research data lifecycle and more broadly.** More specifically, in addition to data curators and repository managers who are directly involved in curating research data, these responsible-contributor roles include: researchers, data stewards and other research support staff, research software developers, and technicians and facilities staff at research performing organizations, as well as funders, publishers, national and international infrastructure initiatives, instrument and tool providers, and professional organizations and scholarly societies.

This list of diverse roles also highlights the considerable range and depth of knowledge and skills collectively required to ensure effective curation of research data today. No professional role and no individual can possess all the necessary expertise to carry out every stage and every aspect of data curation for any disciplines. Rather, different roles and different people bring their unique combinations of knowledge, skills, and experience to the task, and it is only collectively that the aim of effective data curation can be accomplished.

Disciplinary knowledge—whether the content, methodology, or tools and technology used in research—is a crucial aspect of the foundational expertise needed for effective data curation in the given discipline and for the benefit of that scientific community. That disciplinary knowledge often originates from researchers, data stewards, research software developers, and technicians actively involved in research in that discipline. However, it can also come from funders, publishers, national and international infrastructure initiatives, instrument and tool providers, and professional organizations and scholarly societies, as well as from data curators and repository managers at both discipline-specific and generalist data repositories.

In generating the list of responsible-contributor roles to examine in this report, we utilized the [Minimum Viable Skillset \(MVS\)](#) catalogue of [Open Science profiles](#) generated in the Skills4EOSC project, which aimed at supporting the training needs of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).

Below, we describe some of the key roles, including their main activities and responsibilities, and their contribution toward data curation:

- Data curators and repository managers (MVS: Digital Collection Curator)
- Researchers (MVS: Early Career, Senior)
- Data stewards (MVS: Coordinator, Embedded) and other research support staff
- Technicians and facilities
- Research software developers

- Publishers of research (MVS: Scholarly Communications Professional)
- Funders of research
- National and international initiatives (MVS: Research Infrastructure Professional)
- Instrument and tool providers
- Professional organizations and scholarly societies

3.1 Key Roles

3.1.1 Data Curators and Repository Managers

Relevant MVS profile: [Digital Collection Curator](#)

Data curators and repository managers contribute to data curation directly. They work closely with stakeholders to ensure long-term preservation and re-use of research data while also adding value to data collections in the context of both generalist and domain-specific repositories. They are responsible for implementing the FAIR principles for research data and other research outputs and the TRUST principles for trustworthy repositories, for enabling data sharing within and across scientific disciplines, and for advancing Open Science more broadly. Beyond the data repositories, data curators also curate and preserve a wide range of digital information in galleries, libraries, archives, and museums (GLAM).

Main activities and responsibilities of data curators:

- Identify the needs of stakeholders around the sharing, preservation, and reuse of research outputs and develop policies, services, and tools to address these needs
- Support the stakeholders in applying best practices in managing data and other research outputs in their disciplines
- Work with researchers and data stewards to accept deposits of research data and other research outputs into their repositories and collections
- Appraise and re-appraise the data and other research outputs in their repositories and collections to ensure continued value and relevance, completeness of documentation, compliance with laws, sustainability, and potential for reuse
- Adopt relevant infrastructures, tools, and techniques to support effective data curation, preservation, and reuse
- Monitor and comply with laws, regulations, and policies on legal and ethical research behaviour
- Liaise with and support networks of experts and communities of practice in the relevant disciplines
- Hold trainings and events
- Continue to develop relevant knowledge and skills to support high quality and reproducible research

3.1.2 Researchers

Relevant MVS profiles: [Early Career Researcher](#), [Senior Researcher](#)

Researchers generate new knowledge and validate existing knowledge by conducting original and replication research in their disciplines and sharing the research outputs with their scientific communities and the society at large. More specifically, researchers utilize their expertise in the content and methodology of their discipline to design and conduct research projects to answer specific research questions or test specific research hypotheses. These research projects typically include the collection, storage, processing, documentation, and

analysis of research data, collectively referred to as research data management (RDM), as well as the sharing, preservation, and archiving of research data after project completion.

Early career researchers are within 5 to 8 years of their doctoral degree, still developing their independence and building their funding and publication track record, while senior researchers are more established and often direct a research group and lead large research projects. Both groups indirectly enable effective data curation of their research outputs by employing effective data management during their research projects, particularly with respect to appropriate file formats, standard metadata, and careful documentation and process recording. Both groups also serve as research mentors and supervisors to students and postdoctoral fellows and can thus encourage best practices in data management, and by extension in data curation, in the next generation of researchers.

Main activities and responsibilities of researchers:

- Stay current on the knowledge in their discipline, identify knowledge gaps, and generate research questions and hypotheses to generate new knowledge or replicate existing one
- Design, manage, and evaluate research projects in their disciplines
- Apply for and secure ethical approval for their research projects
- Plan and carry out data management tasks during their research projects, including collection, storage, processing, documentation, and analysis of research data
- Interpret the results in the context of existing body of disciplinary knowledge
- Work with funders to prepare funding proposals and secure research funding
- Work with publishers and peer reviewers to prepare research articles for publication
- Work with data curators and repository managers to prepare datasets and other research outputs for sharing and preservation in data repositories
- Train and mentor junior researchers and other research team members
- Continue to develop relevant knowledge and skills to generate high quality and reproducible research

3.1.3 Data Stewards and Other Research Support Staff

Relevant MVS profiles: [Coordinator Data Stewards](#), [Embedded Data Stewards](#)

Data stewards work with stakeholders to establish, govern, and maintain processes for research data management (RDM) across the data lifecycle, including data collection, storage, processing, documentation, and analysis during the project activities, as well as data sharing and data reuse near or after the project completion. Data stewards in the Coordinator role support RDM for the entire organisation and across multiple disciplines, while data stewards Embedded in a specific research team work closely with that team and provide the RDM support that is tailored to their projects, whether discipline-specific or cross-disciplinary.

Both types of data stewards indirectly enable effective data curation by employing effective data management in the organizations and research projects they support, particularly with respect to appropriate file formats, standard metadata, and careful documentation and process recording. Both types of data stewards, but particularly those in the Coordinator role, also deliver research-related training to both researchers and trainees, and thus can encourage best practices in data management, and by extension in data curation, in their respective contexts.

Main activities and responsibilities of data stewards:

- Work with researchers to plan and carry out RDM tasks during the research projects, including collection, storage, processing, documentation, and analysis of research data
- Adopt relevant infrastructures, tools, and techniques to support effective RDM
- Contributes to the development, implementing and monitoring of institutional RDM and Open Science policies and data governance, together with tools and services to support these
- Communicates the importance of FAIR principles and Open Science principles to all levels within the organization
- Work with researchers as well as data curators and repository managers to prepare datasets and other research outputs for sharing and preservation in data repositories
- Work with data repositories, publishers, and funders to monitor data sharing and reuse and to establish and promote best practices
- Manage, monitor, and evaluate research projects
- Monitor and comply with laws, regulations, and policies on ethical research conduct
- Liaise with data stewards and similar research support roles at other organizations to exchange knowledge and build a community of practice
- Design, deliver, and evaluate training on RDM, Open Science, and related topics
- Continue to develop relevant knowledge and skills to support high quality and reproducible research

3.1.4 Technicians and Facilities

Technicians, research technical professionals (RTPs), and facilities work with researchers and other stakeholders to establish and maintain the processes for data collection using discipline-specific instruments, techniques, and best practices. They are experts in using and maintaining the instrumentation and possess the technical knowledge to carry out RDM tasks early in the research data lifecycle. By implementing best practices in RDM from the start of the project they can also set the foundation for effective data curation later in the research data lifecycle.

Main activities and responsibilities of technicians, RTPs, and facilities:

- Conduct data collection for research projects
- Carry out RDM tasks early in the research data lifecycle, including the collection, storage, and processing of research data as well as the appropriate documentation
- Provide technical expertise to use and maintain instruments
- Continue to develop relevant knowledge and skills to support high quality and reproducible research

3.1.5 Research Software Developers

Research software developers work with other stakeholders to develop, test, and maintain research software as part of research projects. They provide the technical expertise to create and improve software and infrastructure tools that are increasingly important at all stages of RDM, from the collection and storage through processing and analysis to the sharing and preservation of research data. By implementing best practices in research software development, including FAIR and Open Science principles, from the start of the project they also set the foundation for high quality and reproducible research outputs and for effective data curation later in the research data lifecycle.

Main activities and responsibilities of research software developers:

- Work with researchers to develop, test, and maintain research software tailored to the needs of specific research projects as well as disciplinary and institutional context
- Apply FAIR principles and Open Science principles to research software
- Contribute to open-source projects and share research software with wider community
- Continue to develop relevant knowledge and skills to support high quality and reproducible research

3.1.6 Publishers

Relevant MVS profile: [Scholarly Communications Professional](#)

Publishers work with other stakeholders to publish and disseminate the outputs of research activities, including research articles via academic journals and other forms of scholarly communications. They are responsible for defining and implementing disciplinary standards, peer review processes, and Open Science policies to ensure high quality and reproducibility of research outputs and to maximize the value of the research to the scientific community and society at large. They can promote and encourage best practices in data curation via their requirements and recommendations for the publication of research outputs as well as through collaborations with other stakeholders.

Main activities and responsibilities of publishers:

- Manage, monitor, and evaluate the publication process (digital and print) of a variety of research outputs, including articles and books
- Edit research articles, books, and other research outputs to ensure their high quality and reproducibility
- Maintain or use a digital publishing platform
- Communicate with researchers (as authors and peer reviewers), data repository managers, librarians, IT professionals, legal experts, and other stakeholders
- Apply FAIR principles, Open Science principles, as well as relevant laws, regulations, and policies to the publication, curation, and dissemination of research outputs
- Collaborate with research performing institutions and data repositories
- Establish and enforce relevant policies and guidelines
- Hold trainings and events
- Continue to develop relevant knowledge and skills to support high quality and reproducible research

3.1.7 Funders

Funders work with research performing organizations and other stakeholders to provide funding for research projects, thus enabling the generation and replication of new knowledge as well as technical innovation and culture change in their target disciplines. Whether government agencies, industry sponsors, or private foundations, funders can promote and enforce best practices in RDM and data curation, including implementation of FAIR and Open Science principles, via their requirements and selection criteria.

Main activities and responsibilities of funders:

- Set funding priorities for specific research disciplines
- Formulate funding calls, including specific goals, requirements, and selection criteria, and use them to evaluate applications and distribute funding

- Maintain or use a funding application platform and other financial and reporting tools
- Monitor and evaluate progress of funded research projects via reports and other metrics, including on their compliance with Open Science requirements
- Liaise and collaborate with research communities, including research performing organizations, professional organizations, and research publishers
- Hold trainings and events
- Continue to develop relevant knowledge and skills to support high quality and reproducible research

3.1.8 National and International Infrastructure Initiatives

Relevant MVS profile: [Research Infrastructure Professional](#) (see also [Carrer Accelerator for Research Infrastructure Scientists](#))

National and international initiatives, including those centered on research infrastructure, work with researchers, data stewards, data curators, publishers, and other stakeholders to support and advance high quality and reproducible research in their target disciplines by addressing their community's needs and challenges around RDM and data curation.

Main activities and responsibilities of national and international initiatives:

- Develop, test, and maintain an infrastructure platform to address the needs and challenges of their target research community around RDM and data curation
- Develop, test, and maintain any necessary tools, services, policies, guidelines, trainings and other offerings to extend the functionality and usefulness of the infrastructure platform to the target research community
- Incorporate FAIR principles, Open Science principles, as well as relevant laws, regulations, and policies in all their offerings
- Liaise and maintain open communication with the target research community, including researchers, data stewards, technicians and facilities, research software developers, data curators and repository managers, and other stakeholders
- Collaborate and exchange knowledge with sister initiatives in other countries or other disciplines (e.g., PSDI's collaboration with BioFAIR in the UK)
- Facilitate trust, collaboration, and knowledge exchange between the stakeholders in the target research community
- Hold trainings and events
- Continue to develop relevant knowledge and skills to support high quality and reproducible research

3.1.9 Instrument and Tool Providers

Typically operating in the commercial sector, instrument and tool providers are responsible for designing, manufacturing, testing, and maintaining instruments, tools, and software for use in research. By implementing best practices in RDM in the design and operation of the research instruments and software, they can set the foundation for effective data curation later in the research data lifecycle.

Main activities and responsibilities of instrument and tool providers:

- Design, manufacture, test, and maintain instruments and software to address the needs and challenges of their target research community around RDM and data curation

- Liaise and maintain open communication with the target research community, including researchers, data stewards, technicians and facilities, research software developers, data curators and repository managers, and other stakeholders
- Hold trainings and events
- Continue to develop relevant knowledge and skills to support high quality and reproducible research

3.1.10 Professional Organizations and Scholarly Societies

Professional organizations and scholarly societies establish, maintain, and promote the disciplinary standards, guidelines, and best practices in data curation and other research activities while also providing and curating domain-specific training and other resources, organizing events, and serving as a community hub for the expert practitioners and trainees in the given field.

Main skills of professional organizations and scholarly societies:

- Communicate with researchers, data stewards, research technicians, data repository managers, librarians, IT professionals, legal experts, and other stakeholders
- Collaborate with research performing institutions, data repositories, publishers, and funders
- Establish, maintain, and promote relevant disciplinary standards, guidelines, and best practices
- Provide and curate domain-specific training and other resources
- Organize events to bring the community together and facilitate knowledge exchange, networking, and collaboration
- Continue to develop relevant knowledge and skills to support high quality and reproducible research in the given field

3.2 How PSDI Can Support and Collaborate with Practitioners

Although the different roles described above vary in their main activities, responsibilities, and skills, PSDI can support and collaborate with them in similar ways, which produces the additional advantage of connecting the respective professional groups and facilitating knowledge exchange and community building between them, rather than encouraging silos.

Specifically, PSDI can:

- Provide a platform for validated discipline-specific data, resources, services, and tools
- Contribute to the development and maintenance of discipline-specific metadata schema, ontologies, and other semantic artifacts
- Offer reliable and up-to-date training, including on new developments, challenges, and opportunities in RDM and related topics
- Organize in-person and online events for knowledge exchange, networking, and community building between researchers and other stakeholders

These suggestions reflect PSDI's outputs manifest in [the PSDI Knowledge Base](#) and the role it is already playing to provide a focal point for the diverse community of practitioners who engage in curation of Physical Sciences data. It is important that PSDI continues to cultivate this community and identify how best to develop its services to support their needs.

4 Reference Frameworks

Here we review widely adopted frameworks used to drive best practices relating to research data with the aim of identifying aspects of specific relevance to data curation. Following this we offer suggestions that could specifically support those involved in curating Physical Sciences data.

4.1 FAIR Data Principles

The [FAIR Guiding Principles](#) for scientific data management and stewardship were formally published in 2016 and since then have been widely adopted across domains and by communities including academia, industry and policy makers. They define criteria that should be adopted to ensure that data are [Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable](#) by machines as well as humans. Their application has also extended beyond research data to research software, workflows, machine learning (ML) models, and other research products.

The following are key aspects of the FAIR principles that need to be considered in the context of data curation.

FINDABLE	F1. Assign a globally unique and persistent identifier to data and metadata
	Often expected to be a digital object identifier (DOI) but other persistent IDs (PIDs) are available. Also, a repository accession ID combined with the identifiers.org service can provide the uniqueness and resolvability expected.
	F2. Data are described by rich metadata
	Requires application of domain and cross-domain metadata standards that support findability within and across domains. For reuse, requires attributes that enable a researcher to decide whether data are fit for their purpose – context and quality indicators are key here. A challenge is accruing and retaining metadata along the research lifecycle.
ACCESSIBLE	F4. Metadata registered or indexed in a searchable resource
	When generating DOIs, registration agencies such as DataCite will allow metadata to be registered to aid in the discovery of datasets and connections to other data objects. This will tend to be general metadata so additional indexing is necessary to enable domain-specific discovery across domains – the PSDI Cross Search is a good example of a service that enables this.
	A1. Metadata/data retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol
ACCESSIBLE	Accessibility in FAIR relates to the mechanisms by which data are accessed and has less to do with curation activities. Authorisation and authentication are necessary if there are restrictions on use of data – these could be because it contains sensitive data or because of licensing restrictions. A role of curation is to make sure any constraints are clearly articulated.
	A2. Metadata accessible even when data are no longer available

	More of a preservation issue relating to choices made about where to store curated metadata. DataCite metadata store helps satisfy this to some degree, but this may be limited to general metadata.
INTEROPERABLE	I1. Metadata/data use a broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
	Whilst this can relate to domain-specific standards such as Crystallographic Information Framework (CIF), the FAIR Principles focus on more general semantic frameworks such as Resource Description Framework (RDF), OWL, and JSON-LD. Representing data in these frameworks makes it easier to integrate knowledge across domains – physical scientists are less likely to be familiar with these frameworks than standards specific to their domain.
	I2. Metadata/data use FAIR vocabularies
	Regardless of the language used for knowledge representation, data items should ideally be specified according to a vocabulary relevant to a domain.
	I3. Qualified references to other data/metadata
	Critical here is associating standard identifiers which identify elements of a data object – people (ORCID), institutions (ROR), projects (RAID), samples (IGSN, RRID), instruments (PDINST), chemical structures (InChI), as well as DOIs for data and articles. Services that help establish connections that may not be explicitly indicated are also important (for example ScholeXplorer from OpenAIRE, UniChem from EBI).
REUSABILITY	R1.1 Metadata/data are released with a clear and accessible data usage license
	A key part of curation is being clear about rights associated with a dataset.
	R1.2 Metadata/data are associated with detailed provenance
	Many aspects to provenance – who was involved but also how dataset came into being; capturing the software, workflows and models is an important part of satisfying this.
	R1.3 Metadata/data meet domain-relevant community standards
	A challenge here can be the availability and maturity of specific domain standards.

4.1.1 FAIR for AI and AI for FAIR

The FAIR Principles are increasingly applied to software, algorithms, workflows, and artificial intelligence (AI) models in research contexts. In particular, there is a growing need for the AI models and other AI tools used in research to be FAIR as well, consistent with the fully reproducible and reusable research paradigm of Open Science.

With respect to machine learning (ML) and other AI models, FAIR research data is relevant in two distinct ways. On the one hand, FAIR data can reduce the need for data cleanup and improve the quality, reproducibility, and interpretability of the model outputs; while on the other hand, ML/AI tools can be used to help make research data FAIR (e.g., by generating domain-specific metadata). This bidirectional influence between FAIR data and AI models has been captured in the phrase “[FAIR for AI](#) and AI for FAIR.”

4.1.2 Recommendations for PSDI

Consideration of how the FAIR principles and data curation activities intersect leads us towards the following suggestions for activities that would support those involved in curating Physical Sciences data where PSDI could play a role.

Best practices around Persistent Identifiers

- Guidelines for the metadata that should be registered alongside PIDs to enhance the findability of datasets whether in domain, institutional or general data repositories (F1). Worth noting here that we do not suggest PSDI takes on responsibility for assigning DOIs to datasets unless it is willing to take on a long term commitment to maintaining metadata and access to data.
- Encouraging adoption of standard identifiers for objects relevant to the Physical Sciences including instruments, samples, and chemical structures, as well as datasets and documents (I3).

Awareness, adoption and development of metadata standards:

- Ensuring awareness of relevant domain metadata standards and participating in the development of new standards (F2, R3).
- Promoting concepts of [FAIR vocabularies](#) and their application to semantic artefacts in the Physical Sciences (I2).

Technical services

- Development and deployment of indexing services that allow data to be searched at a domain-specific level, i.e. [the PSDI Cross Data Search service](#) (F3).
- Explore if there is a need that PSDI could satisfy for archival services that support accessibility of metadata for physical sciences data objects beyond their lifetime (A2).
- Support for the translation of domain (meta)data into more broadly applicable languages for knowledge representation and the adoption of ontologies needed to enable this (I1).
- Engaging in the development of services that can infer links between data objects, for example taking forward ideas around a resolver for chemical structures (I3).

Research Workflows

- Continue to promote the use of digital research notebooks to accrue metadata across the research lifecycle (F2, R1.3).
- Encouraging the capture of comprehensive provenance information, in particular the software, workflows and models involved in generating datasets (R1.2).

Licensing guidelines

- Continue to provide recommendations to the community on appropriate licences for data and how to express these in ways that can be interpreted by machines (A1, R1.1).

4.2 The TRUST Principles and Related Frameworks

The [TRUST Principles](#) are a set of guidelines aimed at demonstrating digital repository trustworthiness. The five TRUST Principles are as follows:

Principle	Guidance for Repositories
Transparency	To be transparent about specific repository services and data holdings that are verifiable by publicly accessible evidence.
Responsibility	To be responsible for ensuring the authenticity and integrity of data holdings and for the reliability and persistence of its service.
User Focus	To ensure that the data management norms and expectations of target user communities are met.
Sustainability	To sustain services and preserve data holdings for the long-term.
Technology	To provide infrastructure and capabilities to support secure, persistent, and reliable services.

Designed to be complementary to the FAIR Data Principles, the TRUST Principles provide a common framework to generate discussion around best practices and implementation strategies in digital preservation and data stewardship. Whilst the principles are informed by the perspectives of stakeholders across the data management lifecycle, trust is essential to the data curation process, and these principles serve to guide data repositories in both what they offer and how to communicate it.

Transparency about what curation services and tools are being provided allows researchers to make informed decisions about where they deposit their data. Demonstrating responsibility for continued stewardship of data shows that curation will continue to adhere to community norms and standards, which is underlined by an understanding of the designated community and how developments to these standards will evolve over time. The question of reuse and interoperability also brings into focus questions regarding sustainability and technology, and the need to demonstrate that a repository can provide continued and uninterrupted access to data over time.

4.2.1 CoreTrustSeal Criteria

[CoreTrustSeal](#) is certification that assesses the trustworthiness of digital repositories based on the TRUST Principles. Certification criteria have been developed in consultation with the community and are, as such, dynamic and constantly evolving.

CoreTrustSeal criteria: Curation levels

One of the 16 requirements that make up the CoreTrustSeal criteria asks applicants to demonstrate how they ensure the long-term preservation of the digital objects they curate by identifying the different levels of data curation that they currently undertake. Data repositories that applied for certification under the 2023-2025 criteria were asked to select one of the following levels to describe their curation practices:

- A. Content distributed as deposited
- B. Basic curation – e.g., brief checking, addition of basic metadata or documentation
- C. Enhanced curation – e.g., conversion to new formats, enhancement of documentation
- D. Data-level curation – as in C above, but with additional editing of deposited data

For the updated [2026-2028 criteria](#) the CoreTrustSeal board has approved a reframing of the curation levels as “Levels of Curation and Preservation”, and a broader reformulation of how the levels themselves are defined. The approved update to these levels:

- Z. Level Zero. Content distributed as deposited. Unattended deposit-storage-access.
- D. Deposit Compliance.
- C. Initial Curation.
- A. Active preservation.

The revised formulation of expert-level of curation as “active preservation” suggests a greater focus on evidence and documentation to describe the different types of documentation an organisation can provide, with different types of evidence needed for different levels of curation. This increased focus acknowledges the difficulties inherent in attempts to capture different curation practices and provide definitions that are relevant to both domain-specific and generalist data repositories.

Both the current and proposed approaches to defining curation levels encourage the idea that the levels may be cumulative and that a repository can offer different levels of curation for different digital objects, however the proposed changes may make it easier to demonstrate this. The proposed changes to the terms of the different curation levels are accompanied with expanded definitions of these terms, and a clearer specification of curation and preservation levels.

It can be challenging for repositories to describe expert-levels of curation in a self-assessment exercise. The expanded definitions of the higher levels would not only allow greater space to distinguish between the types of curation generalist and disciplinary repositories are undertaking but also encourage applicants to better represent the level of care provided at individual object level.

CoreTrustSeal criteria: Designated Community

The emphasis on “active preservation” that underscores these proposed changes brings into focus another constituent requirement of the CoreTrustSeal criteria: the need to demonstrate an understanding of a repository’s “Designated Community.” Applicants must identify how the specific curation activities undertaken meet the needs of those the actions are undertaken for. This requirement already encourages description of the designated community’s composition, knowledge base, and needs (and why these may change over

time), but the focus on “active preservation” demands specific demonstration that a repository understands reuse purposes and scenarios, takes long-term responsibility for ensuring data reuse, and anticipates when and why these purposes may change in the future.

4.2.2 Current European Project Landscape

There are two current EOSC (The European Open Science Cloud) projects, [FIDELIS](#) and [EDEN](#), that are aiming to promote transparency, interoperability, and long-term access to research data through a coordinated European network of trustworthy digital repositories based on shared standards, practices, and infrastructure.

[FIDELIS](#) (Federated Infrastructure for Digital repositories Ensuring Long-term Integrity and Sustainability) is focused on helping repositories communicate their practices, policies, and service levels, align with common standards, improve interoperability, and foster trust across the EOSC ecosystem. Central to this approach is the recognition that curation plays a vital role in ensuring data quality, usability, and long-term value, making it a key mechanism for transparency and trust.

FIDELIS has established a [Transparent Trustworthy Repository Attributes Matrix \(TTRAM\)](#) that provides a reference framework for future activities. A key component of this are “levels of retention, curation and preservation” (or LoRCAP) which are very much based on the revised CoreTrustSeal curation levels discussed above.

[EDEN](#) (European Digital Ecosystem Network) complements FIDELIS by focusing on strategies, tools, and frameworks for identifying, curating, and preserving data that are most valuable for long-term access and reuse. While FIDELIS builds the network and trust framework for digital repositories, EDEN provides the technical and methodological foundation to assess data quality, automate preservation actions, and support decision-making around what data should be preserved.

EDEN has defined 30 [Core Preservation Processes](#) (CPPs) that specify actions necessary for trustworthy digital archiving. These are technical in nature and focus on the operational activities necessary to ensure that the right data are preserved effectively.

Within EDEN is a Work Package (WP3) focused on discipline-specific requirements, validation and future use. WP3 intends to define discipline-specific requirements for long-term preservation and data quality, and to empower discipline and data type-oriented communities to adopt, extend and use the long-term preservation frameworks and tools that EDEN is developing.

4.2.3 Recommendations for PSDI

The guidance and best practices reflected in the CoreTrustSeal criteria and similarly aligned projects are primarily aimed at organisations and projects that are establishing and running data repositories, whether general-purpose or domain-specific. While we recognize that this is not a core activity of PSDI, we do recommend that PSDI cultivate awareness of the key principles for enabling trustworthy curation of data.

If PSDI is to provide archival services to support long-term access to the curated data outputs of Physical Sciences research, then it should look to draw on and implement recommendations such as EDEN’s CPPs.

PSDI should further make sure that its user communities are aware of how wider principles of Trust reflected by CoreTrustSeal and FIDELIS are relevant to them and reflect on services it could provide to enable communities to meet these, particularly in domain curation.

5 Data Curation Case Studies from across Domains

This section describes case studies and experiences from across organisations and disciplines captured during events organised to inform this report. These highlight factors that have contributed to success, areas that need consideration and ways in which initiatives have organised to address challenges collaboratively. Each of these we believe offers inspiration that PSDI could draw on when it comes to thinking about its priorities for supporting data curation and how it might engage wider communities and stakeholders in addressing these.

5.1 Lessons from Crystallography

The development of data publishing in crystallography and the benefits of data curation activities undertaken by established data repositories were described in some detail in section 4.3.1 of the PSDI Pilot Case Study on "[The Role of Structure in Physical Sciences Data Management](#)". Here we highlight some of the factors that have helped enable effective curation of crystallographic data, particularly as the number of structures published annually has increasingly grown:

- **Standard semantic file formats** that are widely adopted by researchers in the field as well as by key software tools and platforms
- **Guidance, best practices, and validation services** promoted by learned societies such as the IUCr and adopted by publishers
- Data deposition **workflows** that aim to make it easy for researchers to follow best practices and connect to wider publication workflows
- **Automated tools** that enable the **triage** necessary to prioritise manual curation in the face of increasing throughput (see below)
- Considering **curation throughout the data lifecycle** – from data generation through publication and beyond

The results of curation activities – aggregated collections of data that can be mined for new knowledge and insights – have fuelled the development of sub-disciplines such as solid form and particle informatics. These in turn demonstrate the value of data curation and make it more likely that researchers will be willing to play their part in abiding by best practices.

Considerations that feed into the role PSDI can play to support improved data curation in the Physical Sciences include:

- Support for the development and promotion of new and existing data standards, in particular encouraging adoption by instrument vendors and software developers
- Development and promotion of best practices for data curation and sharing use cases that illustrate why investing time implementing these is worthwhile
- Lobbying of publishers to encourage their adoption of best practices throughout the publication process and provision of workflows that limit technical barriers for researchers

5.1.1 Automated Curation Workflows

Historically, curation of crystal structure data was a manual process that involved extracting data from the literature (essentially retyping lists of coordinates) and reviewing an article for key contextual information. Bespoke software applications were developed over time to support this, but much of the effort fell to expert editors. With advances in crystallographic technology and increases in scientific activity, the number of structures being published reached the point where increasing the number of experts necessary to keep up with throughput was not economically viable. Around this time, the majority of structures were being published digitally in standard formats, such as the Crystallographic Information File (CIF), thus enabling efficiencies for the initial data extraction and ingest stages of the curation workflow. But what of scientific curation stages?

A key aspect of curation of a chemical crystallographic dataset is assigning a reliable machine-readable representation of the molecular components of the crystal structure. This can be time consuming especially for complex metal-organic structures. CCDC has adopted an automated workflow that aims to automatically generate chemical representations of the crystal structure including a chemical diagram and a compound name. This draws on Bayesian probabilities to suggest the most likely correct representation based on the geometry of the structure and prior knowledge in the CSD – it is using machine learning and can be said to be an AI curation workflow.

Crucially, this workflow does not just make a recommendation – it also gives an indication of how reliable it thinks that recommendation is. This reliability score is based on looking at the complexity of the structure but also on the presence of low probability bond lengths, unlikely oxidation states and other empirical factors. This reliability score is then used to prioritise the effort that is subsequently invested by human curators. If the reliability score is low, then they know there would be value in more closely scrutinising the output of the automated process compared to a high reliability score, where only a cursory check should be necessary.

There is currently much discussion about what role AI can and should play in curation of research datasets with generative and agentic AI opening up many possibilities. Where there seems to be broad consensus at the moment is that there remains a need for there to be a human in the loop to verify the outputs of automated pipelines. This is necessary now to assure the ongoing availability of high-quality data that can be used to train reliable models as well as to feedback into the optimisation of automated workflows. In time, many curation activities could be automated without the need for human scrutiny to assure confidence in the outcomes. For now, the mantra should perhaps be “trust but verify.”

Further, it is important to try and prevent communities fostering premature expectations about how AI might be able to help, which are then used as an excuse not to engage in data management and curation activities now. Whether data curation is human-led or machine-driven, the more context that can be accrued across the research lifecycle, the richer and more reusable the end result will be.

An important role that PSDI can play is to develop knowledge and experience around use and limitations of automated curation processes (including AI and ML) in order to engage in and influence discussions about how these approaches can best be applied in the Physical Sciences and more broadly.

5.1.2 Raw Data

A current area of discussion within crystallography is whether or not raw data should be routinely archived. There are reasons why this is a good idea, including:

- When analytical methods are emerging such as electron diffraction and quantum chemistry – having access to the raw data is an important prerequisite to the development of methodologies for interpreting the data
- When the raw data are hard to interpret or have interesting characteristics – others may be able to improve on results derived from these and identify novel insights
- When a sample is unstable or hard to come by, or data was expensive to collect – in these cases it may not be easy to readily recreate the raw data

Offsetting this is the plain fact that many raw datasets may be uninteresting and not useful for future research, particularly when analytical methods are mature and their use routine. This raises questions about whether the costs of storing such data sets can be justified financially and with regard to environmental impact.

A role PSDI could play going forward is to work with scientific communities of practice within the Physical Sciences to help them understand the pros and cons of storing raw, processed and derived data and establish policies appropriate for their methodologies.

5.1.3 Validation

A feature of data curation workflows in crystallography is the adoption of validation tools that aim to assess the consistency and completeness of deposited datasets. Initially motivated by a desire to detect experimental error, today these tools have a role to play in guarding against the publication of datasets that have been fabricated or falsified.

Many journals require crystallographic datasets to have been submitted to validation services prior to publication. In structural biology, this involves depositing with the PDB who then run their data validation pipeline and provide the depositor with a report. For small molecule crystallography, data can be submitted independently to checkCIF by the researcher, or this can be executed as part of deposition into a repository. Journal policies typically require severe alerts generated by checkCIF to either be addressed or explained, although the rigour may depend on how important the crystallography is to the work described in an article.

Crystallographic and some chemistry publishers undertake a more rigorous review of crystallography either as part of their normal editorial and peer review processes or by outsourcing to other organisations. In addition to assessing alerts, they will look for duplicate publications and more critically assess the validity of the final result. In organic chemistry, one publisher undertakes [review of Supporting Information for selected journals](#) to identify inconsistencies that may give cause for concern. Some chemistry publishers provide [checklists for datasets in specific fields](#) including energy storage, solar energy, biomedical studies and machine learning; these aim to improve the reproducibility and quality of published content and reflect a call for [minimum information reporting standards](#) to be integrated into scholarly processes.

A Political Science aside... *In 2014, major political science journals decided that data related to each published paper should be available and issued a joint statement to that effect: The Data*

Access and Research Transparency (DA-RT).¹ *Going beyond that, the journal Political Analysis requires all quantitative analysis to be reproduced before publication. To accomplish this, the authors must share data and code in a dedicated Dataverse instance, and a dedicated Replication. Editor attempts to reproduce quantitative results. The authors may also use [Code Ocean](#) to ensure that their code runs for others. Similar validation workflows are implemented by other core journals in the Political Sciences field... True replicability!*

Subjecting the many hundreds and thousands of diverse datasets published in the Physical Sciences to the rigour seen in Political Science would more than stretch the resources available to support publication of results. But this cannot be an excuse to maintain the status quo – assessment and validation of research data is a necessary part of data curation if we are to have confidence in the validity of wider scientific findings.

PSDI should look to work with communities within the Physical Sciences to encourage adoption of existing reporting standards and development of new ones, seed the translation of these into services that can automatically check dataset against these standards, and lobby for tools and policies to be embedded in processes across the research lifecycle – from data generation through to publication.

5.2 Data Curation at Dryad

Open data repositories and publishing platforms, both domain-specific and generalist, play a key role in enabling and advancing best practices in effective data curation. Initially established as a digital repository for research data in ecology and evolutionary biology in 2007, [Dryad](#) has evolved into a generalist open data publishing platform driven by a strong commitment to open availability and routine reuse of all research data. A pivotal moment in the Dryad history was the release of the [Joint Data Archiving Policy](#) (JDAP) in 2011, a collaborative work of several academic journals and scientific societies which codified the requirement that research data must be preserved and available for reuse as a condition of publication.

Today Dryad is one of the leading open data platforms that serves and represents an international multi-stakeholder community of academic and research institutions, research funders, academic publishers, and scientific societies, and a signatory to the [Principles of Open Scholarly Infrastructure](#) (POSI). The goal is to foster a culture change toward open data and to elevate data to the same status as scholarly publications. Dryad also utilizes and actively advocates for standards in metadata, persistent identifiers, usage and citation metrics, as well as other enhancements to data submission, workflow integrations, and general interoperability, including through multiple collaborations and community engagement. Dryad's approach is to collaborate and integrate with existing services, rather than compete, in order to build a sustainable and frictionless research data ecosystem.

As Jennifer Gibson, the Executive Director of Dryad, stressed in her talk at the PSDI Roadshow event on Data Curation and Management in Physical Sciences in Cambridge in June 2025, data curation is at the heart of Dryad's services. Data curators at Dryad are full-time staff members and undergo extensive training, with multiple checkpoints. Since Dryad is a generalist data platform, serving a wide range of disciplines, the data curation training and

¹ Data Access and Research Transparency (DA-RT): A Joint Statement by Political Science Journal Editors: <https://www.dartstatement.org/2014-journal-editors-statement-jets>

practice are necessarily generalist as well. In addition, both the curation training and the curation services at Dryad are guided by the recognition that data curation is as much about dealing with people as dealing with data. Maintaining trust, open communication, and ongoing collaboration with the target research communities and other stakeholders is crucial to any data publishing platform staying relevant and delivering value to the users.

The curation of research datasets at Dryad involves several steps. The initial data submission requires data files as well as the necessary metadata and a README file. If the data files are associated with a manuscript under review, there is an option to share these data files with peer reviewers. Typically following acceptance for publication, the datasets then proceed to curation at Dryad, starting with ingestion and validation in accordance with the FAIR Principles. The data curators ensure that the data is appropriate and licensed for sharing; that the files are accessible and usable; and that the metadata meets with the quality standards. The authors have an opportunity to revise their data submission based on curator feedback. Finally, once approved by the curators, the data is published on Dryad, ensuring that the data are findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable, and citable. The datasets are assigned digital object identifiers (DOIs) as well as other persistent identifiers (PIDs) and linked to related research objects, all to increase discoverability, enable recognition, and encourage reuse.

An opportunity for PSDI is to explore how it can help general data repositories such as Dryad develop curation processes that maximise the reuse potential of physical data sciences datasets within their collection. This could involve encouraging adoption by depositors of [guidelines emerging from projects relating to FAIR spectroscopy](#) or [creation of templates that help ensure FAIR-compliant metadata at a domain level](#). PSDI and Dryad have been exploring opportunities such as these following on from Dryad's involvement in one of the PSDI Data Curation Roadshows.

5.3 The Data Curation Network

The [Data Curation Network](#) (DCN) is a collaborative, community-led initiative comprising 27 institutions and over 70 data curators primarily from library and information services in the United States. Launched in 2016 and officially established as a member-funded organization in 2021, the network aims to advance open research by making data more ethical, reusable, and understandable. It brings together data stewards and curation practitioners to share knowledge and expertise across different research domains.

The DCN's curation process follows a structured workflow called CURATE(D): Check, Understand, Request, Augment, Transform, Evaluate, and Document. When an institution receives a dataset beyond its internal expertise, it can request support from the network. A coordinator matches the dataset with an appropriate expert curator who then applies this comprehensive workflow.

The network has developed 46 peer-reviewed primers covering various disciplinary areas and curation tasks, which are publicly available on GitHub. These primers provide guidance on handling different types of research data, from file format conversions to metadata enrichment and fairness evaluation.

The network's success lies in its collaborative approach, providing professional development opportunities, sharing expertise across institutions, and offering cost-effective curation support. By creating a community of practice and developing comprehensive resources, the

DCN helps institutions provide high-quality data curation services without individually hiring experts for every domain.

The DCN faces significant challenges, particularly in curating specialized data types. The network's expertise is heavily skewed towards social and behavioural sciences (39%) and life sciences (27%), with only 16% of curators having Physical Sciences expertise. This limitation becomes problematic as more complex data sets from chemistry and materials science emerge.

An opportunity for PSDI is to consider how it might connect into DCN to broaden geographical reach and contribute Physical Sciences expertise to provide additional primers and support with dataset review.

5.4 NFDI4Chem

NFDI4Chem is a national consortium within the German Research Data Infrastructure initiative, established in 2018 and funded by the federal government and states. Whilst primarily comprising major universities and research institutes in Germany, NFDI4Chem aims to be international in outlook connecting with global initiatives such as RDA, IUPAC, and EOSC. It has strategic focus on covering the entire data life cycle in chemistry, particularly for data describing molecules, properties, and reactions.

NFDI4Chem has developed an ecosystem of specialized repositories catering to different chemistry sub-domains, each of which has different approaches to curation. Common to these are a combination of automated processes supported by human review. There are ongoing efforts to explore how AI-based approaches can help streamline and improve curation workflows.

RADAR4Chem: Allows publication of research data across chemistry disciplines. The curator role is delegated to research group experts who can review the quality of the data and the metadata. They are assisted by a Metadata Editor that suggests relevant terms from NFDI4Chem's Terminology service. Work is underway to develop further AI-based tools that can help with metadata enhancement and incorporate an AI-based evaluation of the FAIRness of a dataset.

Chemotion Repository: A repository for samples, reactions, and related research data. Supports several levels of data checking to verify that files are in standard readable formats, and that data are complete, consistent and plausible. Whilst some of this is undertaken automatically, a team of curators that supports this process - currently eight editorial reviewers joined by additional reviewers from research groups that contribute to Chemotion.

nmrXiv: NMR data is curated through a semi-automatic workflow that combines automatic parsing and enrichment with a Submitter Review. Datasets are uploaded, automatically processed and checked for quality, then further annotated.

STREND A DB: Here, enzyme data are submitted and checked for compliance and then given a DOI. The dataset is provided with a manuscript as part of the journal review process. After a paper is accepted, bibliographic details are added, and the data are validated against the journal article for plausibility before being made public in STREND A DB.

NFDI4Chem has developed a number of tools and workflows that aim to facilitate seamless and trusted management of data across the research life cycle supported by

recommendations and policies that encourage adoption of these. Instilling cultural change remains a challenge with ongoing efforts to educate researchers about data curation and promote electronic lab notebook adoption.

Other NFDI4Chem activities of particular relevance to data curation include their reporting guidelines for providing [Minimum Information about Chemical Investigations \(MIChIs\)](#) and the [NFDI4Chem Terminology Service](#) which provides information about the scope and application of chemistry ontologies.

PSDI has established good relationships with NFDI4Chem which it should continue to cultivate with a view to minimising duplication of effort, sharing experiences, mutual promotion of services, and encouraging international cooperation.

5.5 Biodata Resources – Addressing Continuity Challenges

[FlyBase](#) is a cornerstone of biological research, especially in genetics and developmental biology, due to its comprehensive and curated data on the common fruit fly which is seen as a key model organism for studying human diseases. For over 30 years it has been funded by a grant from the National Human Genome Research Institute in the US. As a result of broad federal funding cuts, [this grant was cancelled in May 2025](#). At risk are the salaries for teams of curators not just in the US but [also in the UK](#). Beyond this human cost is of course the possibility that the data within FlyBase becomes lost to current and future generations.

Challenges in sustaining funding of data resources are not new and various studies have highlighted concerns over a number of years particularly in the life sciences². Some resources have survived as a result of new models being established: as a consequence of funding for The Arabidopsis Information Resource (TAIR) becoming under threat, a non-profit called Phoenix Bioinformatics was established to provide alternative funding models for TAIR and similar databases³. [Drugbank](#) - a comprehensive resource for in silico drug discovery and exploration - turned to a strategy of charging for access to some services and data to survive leading to concerns from some on barriers this may present for reuse⁴.

The [Global Biodata Coalition](#) was formed to work in collaboration with funders to ensure that biodata resources remain freely available to all and avoid the potential loss of resources that would damage both public and private research. As part of its activities, it identifies [Global Core Biodata Resources](#) that are considered of fundamental importance to the wider biological and life sciences. This selection builds on [a process established by ELIXIR for identifying Core Data Resources](#), which additionally identifies Core Deposition Databases that are particularly important for the long-term preservation of data.

A key element of the CoreTrustSeal criteria is the need to ensure that a repository has in place processes that ensure data won't disappear due to technical failure or institutional instability. This includes having disaster recovery plans but also encourages having formal agreements with external partners that could take on hosting of the data in the event of a complete inability to continue operating. Such arrangements can be difficult to establish on paper and even more challenging to establish in practice. In the journal publishing world,

² [Merali & Giles \(2005\)](#), [Nature Cell Biology Editorial \(2006\)](#), [Bastow and Leonelli \(2010\)](#), [Attwood et al. \(2015\)](#)

³ [Reiser et al. \(2016\)](#)

⁴ [Himmelstein \(2016\)](#)

organisations such as [PORTICO](#) and [CLOCKSS](#) exist to provide such backup services and publishers may have arrangements with memory institutions such as national libraries. There is not as well developed ecosystem for data as there is for journal articles.

Through its Pathfinders (now PSDI Partners), PSDI has been successful in supporting and cultivating community activities around the development of curated collections of relating to catalysis, biomolecular simulation, machine learning inter-atomic potentials and NMR crystallography amongst others. Whilst its support for these partners complements other streams of funding it perhaps behoves PSDI to consider what its role should be to help sustain and insure the outputs of these curation activities, particularly as it grows the PSDI Partner network.

Opportunities PSDI might consider:

Services it could offer to provide projects hosting data elsewhere with a fallback archiving mechanism that ensures public access to data in some form if projects become unsustainable or data outputs become in need of rescue. This could additionally help those maintaining repositories comply with CoreTrustSeal criteria around continuity.

Developing criteria and processes for identifying data collections and repositories that are essential to Physical Sciences research.

Cultivating a network that lobbies funders, institutions and other stakeholders to ensure there is adequate and sustained funding for essential data curation activities in the Physical Sciences.

5.6 Discipline-specific Data Management Plans

A Data Management Plan (DMP) is a formal document that outlines how data will be handled throughout a research project or initiative. For more than a decade, DMPs have been required by funding agencies to ensure data is managed responsibly and remains accessible for future use. A DMP will typically include:

- **Data Collection:** What data will be created and how
- **Documentation & Metadata:** How data will be described
- **Ethics & Legal Compliance:** How IP, copyright, and sensitive data are handled
- **Storage & Backup:** How data are stored and access managed
- **Selection & Preservation:** What will be stored long-term and where
- **Data Sharing:** How and when data will be made available
- **Responsibilities & Resources:** Who manages what and associated costs

The activities and responsibilities suggested by a DMP relate to both data management and data curation. There is debate around how effective DMPs have been at improving research practices and improving the availability and reusability of research data beyond the lifetime of a project, with the risk that DMPs become little more than tick box exercises⁵. Further, many DMPs are static PDF documents, limiting their utility in a digital context. This has prompted initiatives to develop and promote “[active](#)” and “[machine-actionable](#)” DMPs that ensure these are dynamic, maintained, and structured for automation.

⁵ See e.g. [Smale et al. \(2020\)](#), [Carlson \(2023\)](#)

Another focus has been on the [development of DMP templates](#) that can be used to focus on the data management and curation considerations of a specific discipline. An interesting consideration here is how to provide something more useful than a generic template in fields where data sets might be very heterogeneous such as the long tail of Physical Sciences. This is a challenge that PSDI has begun to address through the development of a [Data Management Plan for the Physical Sciences](#) building on [work initially undertaken by NFDI4Chem](#).

NFDI4Chem conducted interviews and surveys with physical scientists to understand how they work with data so that they could create a discipline-specific Data Management Plan to support their community. The [Data Management Plan template](#) that they created makes use of discipline-specific metadata and asks questions that reflect the types of activities and data types that are relevant for researchers in chemistry. Discipline-specific guidance and recommendations are also provided, making this a much more valuable tool for those researchers than the generic DMP templates and guidance that are typically available.

Recognising the value of this work, PSDI have taken the NFDI4Chem DMP template as a foundation to create a DMP for the Physical Sciences but have tailored it for the UK audience and also taken into account the requirements from the [Checklist for a Data Management Plan](#) produced by the DCC. In addition to review from the internal PSDI community, the DMP was presented at the Data Curation Roadshow events and additional feedback acquired during both sessions. PSDI continues to actively engage with the community (e.g., at IDCC) to identify ways to evolve DMPs to be more active, interactive, interoperable, smart, and useful tools for researchers and research organisations.

Feedback on the PSDI DMP for Physical Sciences from a small but diverse community attending PSDI Data Curation Roadshow events in 2025 indicated interest in seeing this further developed. We recommend PSDI continue to pursue this, ideally giving consideration to how the end result can be actively maintained and manifested to enable machines to act on outputs associated with a project.

A stretch goal would be to enable a DMP to be automatically generated from a research proposal according to an initial template that is then enhanced through a semi-automated process that guides researcher to elaborate on the data they expect to generate based on their anticipated research process and outcomes. Another enhancement might be inclusion of smart assistants that can help with such tasks as calculating storage costs for the anticipated data collection size.

5.7 Data Curation and the Long Tail of Physical Sciences

The following is a summary of issues inspired by presentations and discussion at an RDA Birds of a Feather session that was part of the International Data Week 2025.

- Data curation is an inherently interdisciplinary activity that cannot be managed effectively by individual researchers alone. The complexity of capturing metadata across diverse tools and workflows requires collaboration between domain experts, software engineers, and data curators.
- Manual data curation is resource-intensive and prone to errors, particularly when dealing with large datasets and complex metadata. To overcome these challenges, connecting data collection and curation activities into automated workflows and electronic lab notebooks is essential.

- A significant barrier to effective data curation is the limited availability of specialized expertise, especially in fields such as chemistry and materials science. Building this capability requires targeted training, the creation of primers and blueprints for data management, and the sharing of validation pipelines across communities.

Although these challenges were raised in the context of the Physical Sciences, they are common across research domains. This highlights the need for cross-disciplinary collaboration and shared solutions rather than siloed approaches.

5.8 Machine-Actionable Data Interoperability in Chemical Sciences

Semantic metadata connects metadata terms to ontologies, thus providing crucial disciplinary context for the research data and enabling their findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reuse (FAIR) in the context of data curation. However, making machine-actionable semantic metadata robust, domain-specific, and machine-actionable remains a challenge.

The Machine-Actionable Data Interoperability in Chemical Sciences ([MADICES](#)) community is an active, international community of practice that has been working to develop, test, and implement standards, tools, and workflows for robust, machine-actionable semantic metadata tailored to chemical sciences, possibly assisted by automation and AI.

MADICES 3 Workshop took place in October 2025 in Villagen, Switzerland, and brought together researchers, data scientists, data stewards, research software developers, data infrastructure providers, industry experts, and other research professionals representing a range of subfields and approaches within the chemical sciences and from several countries. Through a mix of short presentations, group discussions, and working sessions, the participants shared knowledge and collaborated to build and test solutions on topics such as standardisation and best practices, automated annotation, common workflow schemas, interoperability between RDM platforms, integration of new technologies, assessment, as well as community engagement, outreach, and education with respect to machine-actionable semantic metadata in the chemical sciences. Relevant projects and initiatives, both ongoing and completed, were also presented and discussed at the workshop.

PSDI co-organized, sponsored, and actively participated in the MADICES Workshops.

5.9 Cross-domain Interoperability

Research is becoming increasingly cross-disciplinary, presenting additional expectations and requirements on the outputs of data curation. Not only does a curated dataset need to be findable and reusable within a specific domain – it also needs to be manifested in a way that allows it to be discovered from and reused within other domains that may not share the same concepts and languages.

The interoperability criteria of FAIR encourage use of semantic frameworks as a way to bridge across domains. Whilst these capture concepts in a way that should make them easier for machines to translate, they do not address the more practical aspects of interoperability.

The [Cross-domain Interoperability Framework \(CDIF\)](#) aims to provide something more broader and implementation focused by defining profiles for areas such as discovery, access, data description, provenance and context that recommend use of existing standards. The nature standards being suggested (schema.org, DCAT, ODRL, DDI-CDI for example) are very

technical in nature and to understand and implement them requires people expert in data modelling. To expect regular researchers or even data curators to engage directly with these is unrealistic. What is thus required are platforms or workflows that will take care of the translation of domain data into frameworks such as CDIF, such that frictionless flow of data and information across domains can be realised.

A role that PSDI can play here is to explore and encourage the development of platforms that coalesce data from across the Physical Sciences in ways that optimise potential for cross-domain interoperability. This should very much be done having identified some real-world use cases that require cross-domain reuse of Physical Sciences data to avoid investing time in a solution that has only theoretical application.

The PSDI Cross Search service is potentially a platform that could be built on here. Already it is using a common framework (OPTIMADE) to search across sub-domains. An interesting area of exploration could be how domain-specific interoperability frameworks could or should interplay with more general recommendations being developed by CDIF.

6 Recommendations and Next Steps

6.1 Summary of Recommendations

PSDI's remit ideally positions it to be accountable for ensuring that the UK Physical Sciences Community is equipped to curate data to the best possible standards and for identifying gaps in infrastructure and skills that need to be filled. To fulfil this, it is essential that PSDI is empowered by a mandate from funders and backed by funds to undertake activities in this regard.

This does not mean that PSDI should take on the responsibility for undertaking the curation of research data. The breadth of expertise and the time required would far exceed the resources it is likely to be able to command and would not scale. Instead, PSDI should specifically look to support the people who are supporting the researchers with their data curation needs including library staff, dedicated data stewards and facilities managers. Additionally, PSDI should look to instil in researchers an understanding of why data curation is important and the part that they can and should play to enable this.

We have identified six areas where PSDI should focus its activities either because there are unmet needs or opportunities to build on current activities. These are:

- Community Building and Skills Development
- Infrastructure, Tools, Standards and Services
- Promoting and Supporting Standards
- Bridging Industry and Academia
- Policy, Advocacy and Strategic Engagement
- Continuity and Sustainability of Activities

The following section elaborates on each of these areas and provides recommendations for specific activities that PSDI could choose to prioritise. Most of these suggestions are directly

inspired by the areas and initiatives described in the report. The main exception to this is recommendations relating to engagement with industry. These were inspired by CCDC's experience of engaging with industry and involvement in wider initiatives where industry is represented.

6.2 Specific Recommendations

6.2.1 Community Building and Skills Development

PSDI should act as a central hub for data stewardship in the Physical Sciences, fostering collaboration, sharing best practices, and building skills. This includes connecting individual practitioners and community groups, aligning with existing initiatives, supporting training and competency development, and exploring networks that will improve practices across communities.

It is evident that there those who contribute to the curation of data in the Physical Sciences are spread across roles, departments and organisations. There is both a need and an opportunity for PSDI to bring this disparate community together to foster a sustainable and collaborative data curation culture. Specifically, PSDI should:

- R1. Develop and support a community of data stewards in Physical Sciences by serving as a community hub for knowledge exchange, networking, and collaboration.
- R2. Organize webinars, conferences, and other events that bring together those curating data in the Physical Sciences to share knowledge and experiences.
- R3. Understand how PSDI could be a focal point for enabling facility managers at institutions to share their data curation challenges and developing their contribution in this area.
- R4. Look to establish criteria and processes for identifying data collections and repositories that are core to Physical Sciences research communities.
- R5. In partnership with DCC and others, explore creation of a network of UK repository managers to share experiences across domains.
- R6. Explore synergies with existing data curation initiatives such as the Careers and Skills for Data-Driven Research ([CaSDaR](#)) project and the Data Curation Network.
- R7. Define essential skills and knowledge required for effective data curation and help develop training programs for data curators.
- R8. Consider whether there would be value in working towards a professional society dedicated to Physical Science curators.

6.2.2 Infrastructure, Tools, Standards and Services

PSDI should continue to develop domain-specific tools and workflows that support curation and curators across the research data lifecycle from planning through data collection to downstream discovery and reuse. It should continue to provide supporting tools such as converters and discovery services and help develop an understanding of how automation can be responsibly applied to curation.

Considering data curation across the research lifecycle maximises the chances of getting input into curation from those who possess most domain expertise, i.e. the researchers who generate and work with the data. Time and lack of data stewardship skills can be barriers to this but embedding existing principles and enablers in platforms and workflows that researchers interact with as part of their regular work can help overcome these. Specifically, PSDI should:

- R9. Continue to engage in the development of services that support the generation of active Data Management Plans tailored to Physical Sciences.
- R10. Collaborate with instrument vendors and platform providers to establish digital workflows that capture provenance and support curation of data across the research lifecycle.
- R11. Continue to provide tools such as format converters that support the adoption of open standards for metadata and data.
- R12. Develop tools, services and guidance that can help translate domain data into common knowledge representation frameworks and apply ontologies to enable cross-domain reuse.
- R13. Continue to develop cross data search and discovery services tailored to the needs of researchers in the Physical Sciences to aid with discovery of curated data.
- R14. Lead activities that explore how machine learning and other AI approaches can help with the data curation process whilst ensuring transparent and reliable outcomes.

6.2.3 Promoting and Supporting Standards

PSDI should promote adoption of existing standards for metadata and data and dedicate resources to support the development and adoption of new ones. It should help communities develop guidelines for how to apply existing standards and encourage adoption of standard identifiers. It should engage with publishing organisations to encourage the implementation of frameworks that support discovery and aggregation of Physical Sciences data.

Critical to successful outcomes from data curation is the broad adoption and application of standards. Whilst standards should be rooted in the domains they apply to, translating expert knowledge into technical frameworks requires support and facilitation. Those running general data repositories will benefit from expert guidance in how to best implement domain-specific standards in their workflows. Specifically, PSDI should:

- R15. Support initiatives aimed at developing, promoting and sustaining data standards, FAIR vocabularies and interoperability frameworks by contributing dedicated resource to help advance these.
- R16. Help communities establish the essential domain metadata that should be registered alongside persistent identifiers and made readily available alongside a dataset.
- R17. Encourage the adoption of standard identifiers for artefacts beyond datasets and documents including instruments, samples and chemical structures.
- R18. Explore partnerships with data publishing platforms to help them implement standard frameworks such as OPTIMADE and FAIRSpec that will enable the

aggregation of datasets from heterogeneous repositories into homogeneous data collections.

- R19. Provide recommendations to the community on appropriate licenses for data and how to express these in ways that can be interpreted by machines.

6.2.4 Bridging Industry and Academia

PSDI should engage with industry to understand the implications of their data reuse needs for curation, and to identify skills needed for researchers moving into industry roles. It should look for opportunities to engage industry in addressing shared data-related challenges and explore potential services for industry that could generate revenue to complement other funding streams.

The value of the research data generated through academic research to economies is increased when it can be readily reused by industry to address challenges and fuel innovation. To bridge sectors and enhance impact, PSDI should:

- R20. Engage with industry to understand how they want to reuse data generated by UK academia to advance innovation and what implications this may have for how this is managed and curated.
- R21. Explore common challenges relating to data curation such as chemical structure representation and regulatory compliance.
- R22. Understand and support the development of skills needed for researchers transitioning into industry roles.
- R23. Explore if there are services that PSDI could offer industry that would result in revenue that complements other funding streams.

6.2.5 Policy, Advocacy and Strategic Engagement

PSDI should advocate for sustained investment in data infrastructure and skills, align closely with national Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) efforts, and collaborate with publishers and repositories to improve data publication practices. It should engage actively in global research data initiatives to represent physical sciences needs and learn from other domains.

Creating a culture that places emphasis on the importance of data curation for advancing research across disciplines is vital to cultivating better practices by all who have a role to play in enabling future discovery and reuse of data. This is best done in partnership with like-minded initiatives in order to increase impact and minimise duplication of effort. Specifically, PSDI should:

- R24. Advocate for investment by funders and institutions in sustainable data infrastructure and skills development necessary for effective data curation.
- R25. Work closely with related national efforts including other DRI programmes to align efforts.
- R26. Work with publishers and data repositories to improve practices and policies relating to the publication of data, being sure to align with similar efforts in other regions such as NFDI4Chem.

- R27. Actively collaborate with and participate in global research data initiatives to share and promote activities and needs specific to the Physical Sciences whilst learning from experiences in other domains.

6.2.6 Continuity and Sustainability of Activities

PSDI should embed financial, operational, and environmental sustainability in all initiatives and ensure it has continuity and preservation plans in place. It should also consider how it might be able to act as a backup archive for data in other repositories. It should explore connections to other initiatives that could help ensure preservation of outputs and continuously review community needs to inform development of services in the future.

To ensure long-term success, PSDI should:

- R28. Address financial, operational, and environmental sustainability in all its initiatives.
- R29. Ensure continuity of its services and data preservation infrastructure.
- R30. Explore provision of fallback archiving mechanisms that would allow public access to data or metadata in other resources should it no longer be possible to sustain these.
- R31. Develop criteria and processes for identifying data collections and repositories that are essential to Physical Sciences research.
- R32. Be constantly reviewing user community needs and evolving plans to address these.

6.3 Skills and Expertise Required

Cutting across these areas are three different types of action the PSDI could undertake which may suggest the skills and expertise PSDI will need to maintain or acquire:

Lobbying, advocating, promoting: Engaging and connecting across policy makers (funders, institutions, editorial boards) and infrastructure providers (instrument vendors, software and platform providers, data publishers).

Providing services: Could be technical, could be advisory, could be training, could be community-building. Recognising that resources are likely to be limited, it will be important to focus on what can most effectively benefit the wider Physical Sciences community.

Working in partnership: Some specific suggestions noted include DCC and CaSDaR for training and community building, leveraging outputs of NFDI4Chem, Data Curation Network to develop curation guides, exploring routes (back) into EOSC and related initiatives, working with other UKRI-funded Digital Research Infrastructures (DRIs).

6.4 Next Steps

This report offers many recommendations across six different areas. Some of these reflect what PSDI is already doing, suggesting it is important that these activities continue. Other recommendations suggest additional activities that it will be necessary to prioritise against future goals and available resources.

It will be essential that prioritisation of activities in this area is undertaken in consultation with the wider community to understand what is most important for addressing current

bottlenecks and what could have lasting impact. Ultimately, community need combined with PSDI ambitions and resources will inform which specific activities should be taken forward.

We hope that this report and the suggestions within it will prove useful in helping to shape PSDI's future priorities and may lead to improvements in the curation of Physical Sciences data generated by research communities in the UK and beyond.

7 Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank the following people for their contribution to this report and the activities that inspired it:

- Colleagues from CCDC and DCC for their assistance organising events and for their thoughtful review of the report.
- Cerys Willoughby and Nicola Knight for helping to shape the report and valuable input into planning associated community events.
- Members of the wider community who generously shared their case studies, experiences, and perspectives.

We gratefully acknowledge funding provided by PSDI to support this work through EPSRC grants EP/X032701/1 and EP/X032663/1.